

On The Algebraic Properties of Symbolic 6-Plithogenic Integers

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Abstract: This paper is dedicated to study the properties of symbolic 6-plithogenic integers and number theory, where we present many numbers theoretical concepts such as symbolic 6-plithogenic congruencies, symbolic 6-plithogenic Diophantine equations, and symbolic 6-plithogenic Euler's function with Euclidean division. Also, we present many examples to explain the validity and the scientific contribution of our work.

Keywords: symbolic 6-plithogenic integer, symbolic 6-plithogenic congruencies, symbolic 6-plithogenic division.

Introduction

Symbolic n -plithogenic sets were defined for the first time by Smarandache in [4, 24-25], with many interesting algebraic properties.

In [1-3], the symbolic 2-plithogenic rings were defined as an extension of classical rings. Many results were obtained with respect to their ideals and homomorphisms. The symbolic 2-plithogenic rings and fields have many applications in generalizing other algebraic structures such as symbolic 2-plithogenic vector spaces, symbolic 2-plithogenic modules, and symbolic 2-plithogenic equations [5-7].

Laterally, many authors defined and studied symbolic 3-plithogenic algebraic structures, such as symbolic 3-plithogenic spaces and modules, see [8, 21-23].

In the literature, the extended integer systems were used in number theory, for example neutrosophic numbers have helped with neutrosophic number theory, refined neutrosophic numbers generated refined number theory and split-complex numbers generated split-complex number theory [9-20].

This has motivated many authors to study symbolic 2-plithogenic and symbolic 3-plithogenic number theoretical concepts such as congruencies, and Diophantine equations [26-36]. The generalized versions of number theoretical concepts are very applicable in other mathematical studies, especially in cryptography.

In this paper, we study the symbolic 6-plithogenic number theoretical concepts for the first time, and we illustrated many examples to clarify the novel approach.

Main discussion

Definition:

The rung of symbolic 6-plithogenic integer is defined as follows:

$$6 - SP_Z = \{x_0 + \sum_{i=1}^6 x_i P_i; x_i \in Z\}, \text{ where } P_i \times P_j = p_{\max(i,j)}, P_i^2 = P_i.$$

Definition.

Let $X = x_0 + \sum_{i=1}^6 x_i P_i, Y = y_0 + \sum_{i=1}^6 y_i P_i, Z = z_0 + \sum_{i=1}^6 z_i P_i \in 6 - SP_Z$, we say that:

- 1). $X \setminus Y$ if there exists $Z \in 6 - SP_Z$ such that $X.Z = Y$.
- 2). $X \equiv Y(mod Z)$ if $Z \setminus X - Y$.
- 3). $Z = gcd(X, Y)$ if $Z \setminus X, Z \setminus Y$ and if $T \setminus X, T \setminus Y$, then $T \setminus Z$.
- 4). X, Y are relatively prime if $gcd(X, Y) = 1$.

Theorem1.

Let $X = x_0 + \sum_{i=1}^6 x_i P_i, Y = y_0 + \sum_{i=1}^6 y_i P_i, Z = z_0 + \sum_{i=1}^6 z_i P_i \in 6 - SP_Z$, then:

- 1). $Z = gcd(X, Y)$ if and only if:

$$\begin{cases} z_0 = gcd(x_0, y_0) \\ \sum_{i=0}^j z_i = gcd\left(\sum_{i=0}^j x_i, \sum_{i=0}^j y_i\right); 1 \leq j \leq 6 \end{cases}$$

- 2). $X \equiv Y \pmod{Z}$ if and only if $\sum_{i=0}^j x_i \equiv \sum_{i=0}^j y_i \pmod{\sum_{i=0}^j z_i}$, where $0 \leq j \leq 6$.
- 3). If $X \setminus Y$ then $\sum_{i=0}^j x_i \setminus \sum_{i=0}^j y_i ; 0 \leq j \leq 6$.

Theorem2.

Let $X = x_0 + \sum_{i=1}^6 x_i P_i, Y = y_0 + \sum_{i=1}^6 y_i P_i, Z = z_0 + \sum_{i=1}^6 z_i P_i, A = a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^6 a_i P_i, B = b_0 + \sum_{i=1}^6 b_i P_i, C = c_0 + \sum_{i=1}^6 c_i P_i \in 6 - SP_Z$, then:

- 1). If $Z \setminus X, Z \setminus Y$, then $Z \setminus AX + BY$.
- 2). If $Z = gcd(X, Y)$, then there exists $A, B \in 6 - SP_Z$ such that $AX + BY = Z$.
- 3). If $X \equiv Y \pmod{Z}$, then:

$$\begin{cases} X + C = Y + C \pmod{Z} & (I) \\ X - C = Y - C \pmod{Z} & (II) \\ X.C = Y.C \pmod{Z} & (III) \end{cases}$$

- 4). X is invertible modulo Z if and only if $\sum_{i=0}^j x_i$ is invertible modulo $\sum_{i=0}^j z_i ; 0 \leq j \leq 6$, and:

$$\begin{aligned} X^{-1} \pmod{Z} = & x_0^{-1} \pmod{z_0} + P_1[(x_0 + x_1)^{-1} \pmod{z_0 + z_1} - x_0^{-1} \pmod{z_0}] + \\ & P_2[(x_0 + x_1 + x_2)^{-1} \pmod{z_0 + z_1 + z_2} - (x_0 + x_1)^{-1} \pmod{z_0 + z_1}] + P_3[(x_0 + x_1 + \\ & x_2 + x_3)^{-1} \pmod{z_0 + z_1 + z_2 + z_3} - (x_0 + x_1 + x_2)^{-1} \pmod{z_0 + z_1 + z_2}] + \\ & P_4[(x_0 + x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4)^{-1} \pmod{z_0 + z_1 + z_2 + z_3 + z_4} - (x_0 + x_1 + x_2 + \\ & x_3)^{-1} \pmod{z_0 + z_1 + z_2 + z_3}] + P_5[(x_0 + x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4 + x_5)^{-1} \pmod{z_0 + z_1 + \\ & z_2 + z_3 + z_4 + z_5} - (x_0 + x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4)^{-1} \pmod{z_0 + z_1 + z_2 + z_3 + z_4}] + \\ & P_6[(x_0 + x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4 + x_5 + x_6)^{-1} \pmod{z_0 + z_1 + z_2 + z_3 + z_4 + z_5 + z_6} - \\ & (x_0 + x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4 + x_5)^{-1} \pmod{z_0 + z_1 + z_2 + z_3 + z_4 + z_5}]. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem3.

Let $AX + BY = C$ be symbolic 6-plithogenic Diophantine equation in two variables, $A, B, C, X, Y \in 6 - SP_Z$, hence it is solvable if and only if:

$$\sum_{i=0}^j a_i \sum_{i=0}^j x_i + \sum_{i=0}^j b_i \sum_{i=0}^j y_i = \sum_{i=0}^j c_i ; 0 \leq j \leq 6 \quad \text{are solvable, i.e.}$$

$$gcd(\sum_{i=0}^j a_i, \sum_{i=0}^j b_i) \setminus \sum_{i=0}^j c_i ; 0 \leq j \leq 6.$$

Theorem4.

Let $X = x_0 + \sum_{i=1}^6 x_i p_i \in 6 - SP_Z$, then:

$$\begin{aligned}
 X^n = x_0^n + P_1 \left[\left(\sum_{i=0}^1 x_i \right)^n - x_0^n \right] + P_2 \left[\left(\sum_{i=0}^2 x_i \right)^n - \left(\sum_{i=0}^1 x_i \right)^n \right] \\
 + P_3 \left[\left(\sum_{i=0}^3 x_i \right)^n - \left(\sum_{i=0}^2 x_i \right)^n \right] + P_4 \left[\left(\sum_{i=0}^4 x_i \right)^n - \left(\sum_{i=0}^3 x_i \right)^n \right] \\
 + P_5 \left[\left(\sum_{i=0}^5 x_i \right)^n - \left(\sum_{i=0}^4 x_i \right)^n \right] + P_6 \left[\left(\sum_{i=0}^6 x_i \right)^n - \left(\sum_{i=0}^5 x_i \right)^n \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem5.

(X, Y, Z) is a symbolic 6-plithogenic Pythagoras triple i.e. it is a solution of the non linear Diophantine equation $X^2 + Y^2 = Z^2$, if and only if $(\sum_{i=0}^j x_i, \sum_{i=0}^j y_i, \sum_{i=0}^j z_i); 0 \leq j \leq 6$ is a Pythagoras triple in Z .

Theorem6.

(X, Y, Z, T) is a symbolic 6-plithogenic Pythagoras quadruple i.e. it is a solution of the non linear Diophantine equation $X^2 + Y^2 + Z^2 = T^2$, if and only if $(\sum_{i=0}^j x_i, \sum_{i=0}^j y_i, \sum_{i=0}^j z_i, \sum_{i=0}^j t_i); 0 \leq j \leq 6$ is a Pythagoras quadruple in Z .

Proof of theorem1.

1). We put

$$\begin{aligned}
 Z = z_0 + \sum_{i=1}^6 z_i P_i, z_0 = gcd(x_0, y_0), \sum_{i=1}^1 z_i = gcd \left(\sum_{i=1}^1 x_i, \sum_{i=1}^1 y_i \right), \sum_{i=1}^2 z_i \\
 = gcd \left(\sum_{i=1}^2 x_i, \sum_{i=1}^2 y_i \right) \\
 \sum_{i=1}^3 z_i = gcd \left(\sum_{i=1}^3 x_i, \sum_{i=1}^3 y_i \right), \sum_{i=1}^4 z_i = gcd \left(\sum_{i=1}^4 x_i, \sum_{i=1}^4 y_i \right), \sum_{i=1}^5 z_i \\
 = gcd \left(\sum_{i=1}^5 x_i, \sum_{i=1}^5 y_i \right), \sum_{i=1}^6 z_i = gcd \left(\sum_{i=1}^6 x_i, \sum_{i=1}^6 y_i \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

Assume that $T = t_0 + \sum_{i=1}^6 t_i P_i$ with $T \setminus X, T \setminus Y$, hence:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \sum_{i=0}^j z_i \setminus \sum_{i=0}^j x_i, \sum_{i=0}^j z_i \setminus \sum_{i=0}^j y_i; 0 \leq j \leq 6 \\ \sum_{i=0}^j t_i \setminus \sum_{i=0}^j x_i, \sum_{i=0}^j t_i \setminus \sum_{i=0}^j y_i; 0 \leq j \leq 6 \end{array} \right.$$

So that $\sum_{i=0}^j t_i \setminus \sum_{i=0}^j z_i; 0 \leq j \leq 6$, hence $T \setminus Z$ and $Z = gcd(X, Y)$.

2). $X \equiv Y(mod Z)$ if and only if $Z \setminus X - Y$, which is equivalent to

$$\sum_{i=0}^j z_i \setminus \sum_{i=0}^j (x_i - y_i); 0 \leq j \leq 6, \text{ hence } \sum_{i=0}^j x_i \equiv \sum_{i=0}^j y_i (mod \sum_{i=0}^j z_i); 0 \leq j \leq 6.$$

3). Assume that $X \setminus Y$, hence:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} x_0 z_0 = y_0 \quad (1) \\ x_0 z_1 + x_1 z_0 + x_1 z_1 = y_1 \quad (2) \\ x_0 z_2 + x_1 z_2 + x_2 z_2 + x_2 z_0 + x_2 z_1 = y_2 \quad (3) \\ x_0 z_3 + x_1 z_3 + x_2 z_3 + x_3 z_3 + x_3 z_0 + x_3 z_1 + x_3 z_2 = y_3 \quad (4) \\ x_0 z_4 + x_1 z_4 + x_2 z_4 + x_3 z_4 + x_4 z_4 + x_4 z_0 + x_4 z_1 + x_4 z_2 + x_4 z_3 = y_4 \quad (5) \\ x_0 z_5 + x_1 z_5 + x_2 z_5 + x_3 z_5 + x_4 z_5 + x_5 z_5 + x_5 z_0 + x_5 z_1 + x_5 z_2 + x_5 z_3 + x_5 z_4 = y_5 \quad (6) \\ x_0 z_6 + x_1 z_6 + x_2 z_6 + x_3 z_6 + x_4 z_6 + x_5 z_6 + x_6 z_6 + x_6 z_0 + x_6 z_1 + x_6 z_2 + x_6 z_3 + x_6 z_4 + x_6 z_5 = y_6 \quad (7) \end{array} \right.$$

By adding (1) + (2), (1) + (2) + (3), (1) + (2) + (3) + (4), (1) + (2) + (3) + (4) + (5), (1) + (2) + (3) + (4) + (5) + (6) , (1) + (2) + (3) + (4) + (5) + (6) + (7) we get:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} x_0 z_0 = y_0 \\ \sum_{i=1}^1 x_i \sum_{i=1}^1 z_i = \sum_{i=1}^1 y_i \\ \sum_{i=1}^2 x_i \sum_{i=1}^2 z_i = \sum_{i=1}^2 y_i \\ \sum_{i=1}^3 x_i \sum_{i=1}^3 z_i = \sum_{i=1}^3 y_i \\ \sum_{i=1}^4 x_i \sum_{i=1}^4 z_i = \sum_{i=1}^4 y_i \\ \sum_{i=1}^5 x_i \sum_{i=1}^5 z_i = \sum_{i=1}^5 y_i \\ \sum_{i=1}^6 x_i \sum_{i=1}^6 z_i = \sum_{i=1}^6 y_i \end{array} \right.$$

Which means that $\sum_{i=0}^j x_i \setminus \sum_{i=0}^j y_i; 0 \leq j \leq 6$

Proof of theorem 2.

1). Assume that $Z \setminus X, Z \setminus Y$, then we get:

$$\sum_{i=0}^j z_i \setminus \sum_{i=0}^j x_i, \text{ and } \sum_{i=0}^j z_i \setminus \sum_{i=0}^j y_i ; 0 \leq j \leq 5.$$

So that $\sum_{i=0}^j z_i \setminus (\sum_{i=0}^j a_i \sum_{i=0}^j x_i + \sum_{i=0}^j b_i \sum_{i=0}^j y_i)$ for $0 \leq j \leq 5$ and $Z \setminus AX + BY$.

2). Assume that $Z = gcd(X, Y)$, then $\sum_{i=0}^j z_i = gcd(\sum_{i=0}^j x_i, \sum_{i=0}^j y_i)$ for all $0 \leq j \leq 5$.

According to Bezout's theorem, we can write:

$$\text{There exists } a_j, b_j \in Z \text{ such that } \sum_{i=0}^j z_i = a_j \sum_{i=0}^j x_i + b_j \sum_{i=0}^j y_i$$

by putting

$$A = a_0 + (a_1 - a_0)P_1 + (a_2 - a_1)P_2 + (a_3 - a_2)P_3 + (a_4 - a_3)P_4 + (a_5 - a_4)P_5,$$

$$B = b_0 + (b_1 - b_0)P_1 + (b_2 - b_1)P_2 + (b_3 - b_2)P_3 + (b_4 - b_3)P_4 + (b_5 - b_4)P_5, \text{ we}$$

get:

$$Z = AX + BY.$$

3). Assume that $X \equiv Y(mod Z)$, then:

$$\sum_{i=0}^j z_i \setminus \sum_{i=0}^j (x_i - y_i) \text{ for all } 0 \leq j \leq 6, \text{ hence:}$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \sum_{i=0}^j z_i \setminus \sum_{i=0}^j (x_i - c_i + c_i - y_i) \\ \sum_{i=0}^j z_i \setminus \sum_{i=0}^j (x_i + c_i - c_i + y_i) \end{array} \right.$$

Hence $X \pm C = Y \pm C(mod Z)$, also:

$$\sum_{i=0}^j z_i \setminus \sum_{i=0}^j (x_i - y_i) \sum_{i=0}^j c_i \text{ i.e. } \sum_{i=0}^j z_i \setminus \sum_{i=0}^j x_i \sum_{i=0}^j c_i - \sum_{i=0}^j y_i \sum_{i=0}^j c_i$$

Hence $X.C \equiv Y.C(mod Z)$.

4). X is invertible modulo Z If and only if there exists $Y = y_0 + \sum_{i=1}^j y_i p_i \in 6 - SP_Z$ such that $X.Y \equiv 1(mod Z)$.

This equivalent to:

$$\sum_{i=0}^j x_i \cdot \sum_{i=0}^j y_i \equiv 1(mod Z) \text{ for } 0 \leq j \leq 6, \text{ hence:}$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^j x_i \text{ is invertible modulo } \sum_{i=0}^j z_i \text{ and:}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 X^{-1} = & x_0^{-1}(\text{mod } z_0) + P_1 \left[\left(\sum_{i=0}^1 x_i \right)^{-1} \left(\text{mod } \sum_{i=0}^1 z_i \right) - x_0^{-1}(\text{mod } z_0) \right] \\
 & + P_2 \left[\left(\sum_{i=0}^2 x_i \right)^{-1} \left(\text{mod } \sum_{i=0}^2 z_i \right) - \left(\sum_{i=0}^1 x_i \right)^{-1} \left(\text{mod } \sum_{i=0}^1 z_i \right) \right] \\
 & + P_3 \left[\left(\sum_{i=0}^3 x_i \right)^{-1} \left(\text{mod } \sum_{i=0}^3 z_i \right) - \left(\sum_{i=0}^2 x_i \right)^{-1} \left(\text{mod } \sum_{i=0}^2 z_i \right) \right] \\
 & + P_4 \left[\left(\sum_{i=0}^4 x_i \right)^{-1} \left(\text{mod } \sum_{i=0}^4 z_i \right) - \left(\sum_{i=0}^3 x_i \right)^{-1} \left(\text{mod } \sum_{i=0}^3 z_i \right) \right] \\
 & + P_5 \left[\left(\sum_{i=0}^5 x_i \right)^{-1} \left(\text{mod } \sum_{i=0}^5 z_i \right) - \left(\sum_{i=0}^4 x_i \right)^{-1} \left(\text{mod } \sum_{i=0}^4 z_i \right) \right] \\
 & + P_6 \left[\left(\sum_{i=0}^6 x_i \right)^{-1} \left(\text{mod } \sum_{i=0}^6 z_i \right) - \left(\sum_{i=0}^5 x_i \right)^{-1} \left(\text{mod } \sum_{i=0}^5 z_i \right) \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof of theorem3.

It is easy to check that $AX + BY = C$ is equivalent to:

$$\sum_{i=0}^j a_i \sum_{i=0}^j x_i + \sum_{i=0}^j b_i \sum_{i=0}^j y_i = \sum_{i=0}^j c_i; 0 \leq j \leq 6$$

The previous six Diophantine equations are solvable if and only if:

$$\text{gcd} \left(\sum_{i=0}^j a_i, \sum_{i=0}^j b_i \right) \mid \sum_{i=0}^j c_i; 0 \leq j \leq 6$$

proof on theorem4.

For $n = 1$, it holds directly.

We assume that it I true for k , we prove it for $k + 1$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 X^{k+1} = XX^k &= \left(x_0 + \sum_{i=0}^6 x_i p_i \right) \left[x_0^k + P_1 \left(\left(\sum_{i=0}^1 x_i \right)^k - x_0^k \right) \right. \\
 &+ P_2 \left(\left(\sum_{i=0}^2 x_i \right)^k - \left(\sum_{i=0}^1 x_i \right)^k \right) + P_3 \left(\left(\sum_{i=0}^3 x_i \right)^k - \left(\sum_{i=0}^2 x_i \right)^k \right) \\
 &+ P_4 \left(\left(\sum_{i=0}^4 x_i \right)^k - \left(\sum_{i=0}^3 x_i \right)^k \right) + P_5 \left(\left(\sum_{i=0}^5 x_i \right)^k - \left(\sum_{i=0}^4 x_i \right)^k \right) \\
 &\left. + P_6 \left(\left(\sum_{i=0}^6 x_i \right)^k - \left(\sum_{i=0}^5 x_i \right)^k \right) \right] \\
 &= x_0^{k+1} + P_1 \left[x_0^k \left(\sum_{i=0}^1 x_i \right)^k - x_0^{k+1} + x_1 x_0^k + x_1 \left(\sum_{i=0}^1 x_i \right)^k - x_1 x_0^k \right] \\
 &+ P_2 \left[x_0 \left(\sum_{i=0}^2 x_i \right)^k - x_0 \left(\sum_{i=0}^1 x_i \right)^k + x_1 \left(\sum_{i=0}^2 x_i \right)^k - x_1 \left(\sum_{i=0}^1 x_i \right)^k + x_2 x_0^k \right. \\
 &\left. + x_1 \left(\sum_{i=0}^1 x_i \right)^k - x_2 x_0^k + x_2 \left(\sum_{i=0}^2 x_i \right)^k - x_2 \left(\sum_{i=0}^1 x_i \right)^k \right] \\
 &+ P_3 \left[x_0 \left(\sum_{i=0}^3 x_i \right)^k - x_0 \left(\sum_{i=0}^2 x_i \right)^k + x_1 \left(\sum_{i=0}^3 x_i \right)^k - x_1 \left(\sum_{i=0}^2 x_i \right)^k \right. \\
 &\left. + x_2 \left(\sum_{i=0}^3 x_i \right)^k - x_2 \left(\sum_{i=0}^2 x_i \right)^k + x_2 x_0^k + x_3 \left(\sum_{i=0}^3 x_i \right)^k - x_3 x_0^k \right. \\
 &\left. + x_3 \left(\sum_{i=0}^2 x_i \right)^k - x_2 \left(\sum_{i=0}^1 x_i \right)^k + x_3 \left(\sum_{i=0}^3 x_i \right)^k - x_2 \left(\sum_{i=0}^2 x_i \right)^k \right] + \dots \\
 &= x_0^{k+1} + P_1 \left[\left(\sum_{i=0}^1 x_i \right)^{k+1} - x_0^{k+1} \right] + P_2 \left[\left(\sum_{i=0}^2 x_i \right)^{k+1} - \left(\sum_{i=0}^1 x_i \right)^{k+1} \right] \\
 &+ \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

And the proof holds.

Proof of theorem5.

$X^2 + Y^2 = Z^2$ implies that:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} x_0^2 + y_0^2 = z_0^2 \\ \left(\sum_{i=0}^1 x_i\right)^2 + \left(\sum_{i=0}^1 y_i\right)^2 = \left(\sum_{i=0}^1 z_i\right)^2 \\ \left(\sum_{i=0}^2 x_i\right)^2 + \left(\sum_{i=0}^2 y_i\right)^2 = \left(\sum_{i=0}^2 z_i\right)^2 \\ \left(\sum_{i=0}^3 x_i\right)^2 + \left(\sum_{i=0}^3 y_i\right)^2 = \left(\sum_{i=0}^3 z_i\right)^2 \\ \left(\sum_{i=0}^4 x_i\right)^2 + \left(\sum_{i=0}^4 y_i\right)^2 = \left(\sum_{i=0}^4 z_i\right)^2 \\ \left(\sum_{i=0}^5 x_i\right)^2 + \left(\sum_{i=0}^5 y_i\right)^2 = \left(\sum_{i=0}^5 z_i\right)^2 \\ \left(\sum_{i=0}^6 x_i\right)^2 + \left(\sum_{i=0}^6 y_i\right)^2 = \left(\sum_{i=0}^6 z_i\right)^2 \end{array} \right.$$

Which implies the proof.

Theorem 6 can be proved by the same argument.

Definition.

Let $X = x_0 + \sum_{i=0}^6 x_i P_i \in 6 - SP_Z$, hence we say that $X > 0$ if and only if $x_0 > 0, \sum_{i=0}^k x_i > 0; 1 \leq k \leq 6$

For example: $X = 3 + P_1 - P_2 + 2P_3 - P_4 - P_5 > 0$, that is because:

$$3 > 0, 4 > 0, 3 > 0, 5 > 0, 4 > 0, 3 > 0.$$

If $Y = y_0 + \sum_{i=0}^6 y_i P_i \in 6 - SP_Z$, we say that $X \geq Y$ if and only if $x_0 \geq y_0, \sum_{i=0}^k x_i \geq \sum_{i=0}^k y_i; 1 \leq k \leq 6$.

For $X = 2 + P_1 + 2P_2 + 5P_3 + P_4 + 6P_5, Y = 1 + P_1 + P_2 + P_3 + 3P_4 + P_5, X \geq Y$, that is because:

$$2 \geq 1, 3 \geq 2, 5 \geq 3, 10 \geq 4, 11 \geq 7, 17 \geq 8$$

Definition.

Let $X = x_0 + \sum_{i=0}^6 x_i P_i, y = y_0 + \sum_{i=0}^6 y_i P_i \geq 0$, hence:

$$\begin{aligned}
 X^Y = x_0^{y_0} + P_1 & \left[\left(\sum_{i=0}^1 x_i \right)^{\sum_{i=0}^1 y_i} - x_0^{y_0} \right] + P_2 \left[\left(\sum_{i=0}^2 x_i \right)^{\sum_{i=0}^2 y_i} - \left(\sum_{i=0}^1 x_i \right)^{\sum_{i=0}^1 y_i} \right] \\
 & + P_3 \left[\left(\sum_{i=0}^3 x_i \right)^{\sum_{i=0}^3 y_i} - \left(\sum_{i=0}^2 x_i \right)^{\sum_{i=0}^2 y_i} \right] \\
 & + P_4 \left[\left(\sum_{i=0}^4 x_i \right)^{\sum_{i=0}^4 y_i} - \left(\sum_{i=0}^3 x_i \right)^{\sum_{i=0}^3 y_i} \right] \\
 & + P_5 \left[\left(\sum_{i=0}^5 x_i \right)^{\sum_{i=0}^5 y_i} - \left(\sum_{i=0}^4 x_i \right)^{\sum_{i=0}^4 y_i} \right] \\
 & + P_6 \left[\left(\sum_{i=0}^6 x_i \right)^{\sum_{i=0}^6 y_i} - \left(\sum_{i=0}^5 x_i \right)^{\sum_{i=0}^5 y_i} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

Definition.

Let $X = x_0 + \sum_{i=0}^6 x_i P_i > 0$, then:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \varphi(X) = \varphi(x_0) + P_1 & \left[\varphi \left(\sum_{i=0}^1 x_i \right) - \varphi(x_0) \right] + P_2 \left[\varphi \left(\sum_{i=0}^2 x_i \right) - \varphi \left(\sum_{i=0}^1 x_i \right) \right] \\
 & + P_3 \left[\varphi \left(\sum_{i=0}^3 x_i \right) - \varphi \left(\sum_{i=0}^2 x_i \right) \right] + P_4 \left[\varphi \left(\sum_{i=0}^4 x_i \right) - \varphi \left(\sum_{i=0}^3 x_i \right) \right] \\
 & + P_5 \left[\varphi \left(\sum_{i=0}^5 x_i \right) - \varphi \left(\sum_{i=0}^4 x_i \right) \right] + P_6 \left[\varphi \left(\sum_{i=0}^6 x_i \right) - \varphi \left(\sum_{i=0}^5 x_i \right) \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

Where φ is Euler's function on Z .

Theorem.

Let $X = x_0 + \sum_{i=0}^6 x_i P_i, Y = y_0 + \sum_{i=0}^6 y_i P_i \in 6 - SP_Z, gcd(X, Y) = 1$ and $X, Y > 0$, hence:

$$X^{\varphi(Y)} \equiv 1 \pmod{Y}$$

Proof.

$$gcd(x_0, y_0) = 1, \text{ hence } x_0^{\varphi(y_0)} \equiv 1 \pmod{y_0}.$$

$$gcd(\sum_{i=0}^1 x_i, \sum_{i=0}^1 y_i) = 1, \text{ hence } (\sum_{i=0}^1 x_i)^{\varphi(\sum_{i=0}^1 y_i)} \equiv 1 \pmod{\sum_{i=0}^1 y_i}$$

By a similar argument, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\sum_{i=0}^2 x_i\right)^{\varphi(\sum_{i=0}^2 y_i)} &\equiv 1 \left(\text{mod } \sum_{i=0}^2 y_i\right), \left(\sum_{i=0}^3 x_i\right)^{\varphi(\sum_{i=0}^3 y_i)} \equiv 1 \left(\text{mod } \sum_{i=0}^3 y_i\right) \\ \left(\sum_{i=0}^4 x_i\right)^{\varphi(\sum_{i=0}^4 y_i)} &\equiv 1 \left(\text{mod } \sum_{i=0}^4 y_i\right), \left(\sum_{i=0}^5 x_i\right)^{\varphi(\sum_{i=0}^5 y_i)} \\ &\equiv 1 \left(\text{mod } \sum_{i=0}^5 y_i\right), \left(\sum_{i=0}^6 x_i\right)^{\varphi(\sum_{i=0}^6 y_i)} \equiv 1 \left(\text{mod } \sum_{i=0}^6 y_i\right) \end{aligned}$$

This implies

$$X^{\varphi(Y)} \equiv 1 + (1-1)P_1 + (1-1)P_2 + (1-1)P_3 + (1-1)P_4 + (1-1)P_5 + (1-1)P_6 \equiv 1 \pmod{Y}.$$

Remark.

We call previous result by symbolic 6-plithogenic Euler's theorem.

Conclusion

In this work, we have studied the properties of symbolic 6-plithogenic integers for the first time, where concepts such as symbolic 6-plithogenic divisors, congruencies, and linear Diophantine equations were handled by many theorems and examples.

Also, we have presented the conditions of symbolic 6-plithogenic Pythagoras triples and quadruples in the corresponding symbolic 6-plithogenic ring of integers.

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